

Variables predicting the association between Autistic Traits and externalizing symptoms among young adults

Abstract

Purpose. Considering the high comorbidity of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) with externalizing disorders and that ASD is considered as a continuum, which implies the identification of its features in the whole population, the purpose of this paper is to know the characteristics of the association of externalizing symptoms in the population with ASD traits.

Design/methodology/approach. One hundred and seventeen postsecondary students participated in the study, providing responses to a battery of self-reported tests.

Findings. The existence of a significant association between ASD and ADHD (.519; $p < .01$) was proved. Regression analyses showed that problems in executive functioning, working memory deficits, and difficulties in the use of ER strategies predicted the presence of ADHD traits ($F = 36.757$, $R^2 = 62.3\%$, $p < .01$) and impulsivity behavior ($F = 18.249$, $R^2 = 45.1\%$, $p < .01$).

Research implications. Externalizing symptomatology in people with higher ASD traits is extended to the general population. Future research should study other problematic behaviors, such as aggression or self-harm, in order to continue generating appropriate interventions.

Originality. The results reported reinforce the study of ASD as a dimensional disorder, in line with the latest advances in the classification of psychopathology. Considering which variables are behind the problematic behaviors, allows interventions to be focused on these factors, contributing to their reduction and to the improvement of professional practices.

Keyword. Broad autism phenotype, externalized comorbidity, Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder, transdiagnosis.

Paper type. Research paper.

Introduction

Advances in the classification of psychopathology show that the current trend is to advocate for a hierarchical-dimensional distribution of disorders (Achenbach et al., 2016; Caspi et al., 2014; Kotov et al., 2017). This classification implies understanding symptoms as levels of severity (Achenbach & Ezpeleta, 2014). In addition, they are useful to explain two realities within psychopathology: comorbidity between disorders and heterogeneity of symptoms (Eaton, 2015; Eaton et al., 2015). Furthermore, the latest edition of the DSM (APA, 2013) recognizes the relevance of the dimensional classifications of psychopathology, contributing to a better understanding of this study. Thus, pathologies such as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) begin to appear in the form of a spectrum, rather than as unique and exclusive diagnoses.

ASD is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by difficulties in social communication and interaction and the presence of restricted and repetitive interests and behaviors. Considering it as a spectrum implies the inclusion of autistic traits in the general population so that the characteristics of ASD extend to the whole population (De Groot & Van Strien, 2017).

This approach is known as the Broad Autism Phenotype (BAP), and refers to the subclinical features of ASD shown by people in the general population (Stewart et al., 2018). These traits are qualitatively similar to difficulties in social communication and to the restricted and repetitive interests and behaviors that characterize ASD. Autism is now understood as a continuum ranging from people who show very light ASD traits to others with a diagnosis and who are severely affected so that all people are located somewhere on this spectrum (De Groot & Van Strien, 2017).

Numerous studies have focused on BAP, studying family members of people diagnosed with ASD (Eyboglu et al., 2017; Losh et al., 2008; McDonnell & Nuttall, 2018), as well as general population. Their results agree in recognition of traits associated with ASD in typically developing population (Landry & Chouinard, 2016). Specifically, it has been shown that people with highest scores on the BAP self-report measures obtain results similar to those who have a diagnosis in some tests such as the figure test, the block task or the Raven matrices (Fugard et al., 2011; Stewart & Austin, 2009; Stewart et al., 2009), concluding that the cognitive and visuospatial performance of this group is similar to that of people with ASD.

It has also been shown that general people with high BAP scores present similar traits to those with ASD in gaze reciprocity (Chen & Yoon, 2011), speech perception, face recognition and body language (Ingersoll, 2010; Stewart & Ota, 2008), and in aspects related to emotions and social relationships (De Groot & Van Strien, 2017; Pisula, et al., 2015). Additionally, they present difficulties in empathy, in the ability of theory of mind (Eyuboglu et al., 2017) and in the regulation of negative emotions (McDonnell & Nuttall, 2018).

Results for characteristics of executive functioning in BAP are inconsistent. Although it has been shown that people who score higher on BAP assessment show more problems in executive functions (EF) (Stewart et al, 2018; Wallace et al., 2016), other investigations have found no relationship between BAP and EF components (Kunihira et al., 2006; Maes et al., 2012; Ridley et al., 2011). This lack of relationship can be explained by the assessment measures employed, which may not be adequately identifying ASD characteristics in general population (Maes et al., 2012; Ridley et al., 2011; Stewart & Austin, 2009).

Autistic traits and externalizing behaviors

ASD rarely appears by itself but rather presents with another associated disorders (Gillberg & Fernell, 2014; Mannion et al., 2014), with externalizing ones being reasonably common (Nunes, 2017). Adults with autism and adults with subclinical autistic traits report greater externalizing behaviors than their peers, but the psychological and transdiagnostic processes underlying these associations are not well understood (Nunes, 2017; Shea et al., 2018).

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is one of the most reported externalizing comorbid disorders in ASD (Kanai et al., 2016; Leader & Mannion, 2016; Visser et al., 2016). The study of its traits in the population with high characteristics of ASD shows similar results to the ones obtained for people with ASD diagnosis.

Research reports that there is an association between both disorders (Panagiotidi et al., 2017; Polderman et al., 2014), so the presence of ASD traits and ADHD traits in the BAP seems to share a nexus underlying both disorders, as it does in people diagnosed with ASD. Bearing in mind that the relationship between ASD and ADHD, although very common, is not clear (Shea et al., 2018) it is convenient to deepen into the transdiagnostic variables that are behind these relationships, acting as mediators,

moderators or predictors of this association. Moreover, considering that both disorders, ASD and ADHD, are understood as psychopathological continuous whose traits are present to a major or lesser extent in the general population (Kotov et al., 2017), we propose the study of externalized comorbidity in adults with ASD symptoms from a transdiagnostic approach.

A transdiagnostic perspective

Transdiagnostic perspective assumes that some latent factors will influence reinforcing or decreasing the relationship between ASD features and ADHD symptoms and its associated behaviors (i.e., impulsivity).

Among these latent transdiagnostic factors, we focus on some of those that the literature has pointed out as explaining the existence of externalizing problems in people with ASD. Firstly, emotion regulation (ER) and its components, such as the use of emotional regulation strategies or emotional control. According to numerous studies (Bos et al., 2018; McDonnell & Nuttall, 2018; Mazefsky et al., 2013; Weiss, 2014) ER can be considered as a potential transdiagnostic factor related to the appearance of externalizing symptomatology in people with ASD traits.

Also, problems in EF, mainly inhibition and working memory, are considered vulnerability factors for the development of externalizing disorders and problematic behaviors (Pinsonneault et al., 2016). Both of these deficits are characteristic of people with ASD traits (Geurts & Lever, 2017; Stewart et al., 2018; Troyb et al., 2014; Wallace et al., 2016), so it is interesting to study the relationship of EF, especially inhibition, working memory or flexibility, with externalizing disorders in people with ASD traits.

The current study. What this paper adds

Post-secondary students are an interesting field in the study of BAP since there are numerous data that report a higher level of ASD traits in those people who focus their studies in areas related to applied sciences, compared to those of social sciences or humanities areas. In different investigations, students in applied science and engineering fields scored higher on the BAP assessment in all cases (De Groot & Van Strien, 2017; Maes et al., 2012; Ridley et al., 2011).

It should be noted that there is evidence that people with high ASD traits are more vulnerable to the development of certain disorders, such as depression, because of awareness of their difficulties and limitations (Barahona-Corrêa, 2017; Tobin et al., 2014). In this sense, it is by having the possibility of knowing the role of the variables that most influence the increase and aggravation of ASD symptoms and of the co-occurring disorders that preventive interventions and treatment actions can be carried out. Besides, genetic influence of ASD makes it possible that the offspring of these people also present features of ASD pathology, which can be aggravated if appropriate preventive measures are not carried out.

Therefore, we propose the following study by which we seek to (1) corroborate the existence of an association between ASD and ADHD symptoms in young adults; and (2) to establish some transdiagnostic variables that may influence the presence of ADHD traits and its related behaviors in this group.

The hypotheses were:

H₁ = A positive and significant relationship is expected between clinical variables (ASD and ADHD) and transdiagnostic variables (difficulties in executive functioning, working memory, inhibition, and use of ER strategies).

H₂ = Transdiagnostic variables (problems in executive functioning, working memory, inhibition and use of ER strategies) are expected to be positive and significant predictors of the association between ADHD features and ASD traits.

Method

Participants

Participants were 117 undergraduate (60 women and 57 men) university (n = 91) and higher professional training students (n = 26) over 18 years old (M = 25.26; SD = 4.63) (Table 1). The inclusion criteria were being 18 and older, being enrolled in higher academic studies and not having ASD, ADHD and/or any other clinical diagnosis.

Potential participants were contacted through a general e-mail describing the study and a link taking them to the study questionnaire that was submitted via virtual campus. This e-mail was also sent to professors in sciences and engineering faculties and other

study centers. Students were asked to participate voluntarily and anonymity was assured. In addition, they were asked for their informed consent.

Materials and design

Demographic variables

This self-report measure consisted of standard demographic questions about gender, age, and other demographic variables, such as the area of knowledge of their studies: social sciences, humanities/arts, health sciences, sciences or engineering.

Autistic Traits

Autism phenotypic traits were measured using the Broad Autism Phenotype Questionnaire (BAPQ; Hurley et al., 2007), a 36-item self-report measure designed to capture autistic characteristics among adults in the general population, through three subscales: rigidity (i. e., *I like to closely follow a routine while working*), pragmatic language (i. e., *People ask me to repeat things I've said because they don't understand*), and distance (i.e., *I would rather talk to people to get information than to socialize*), and a total score (Sasson et al., 2013). Higher scores correspond to a greater presence of symptoms. Average total score was used as an independent variable. We use the Spanish scale (Godoy-Giménez et al., 2017), with an adequate internal consistency ($\alpha = .85$).

Externalizing symptoms (ADHD score, impulsivity and inattention)

Externalizing symptoms were measured using the Conners' Adult ADHD Rating Scales (CAARS-S: S, Conners et al., 1999). The CAARS-S is one of the most commonly used tests for the evaluation of ADHD in adults (Amador-Campos et al., 2014), consisting of 26 items. It is made up of four subscales: impulsivity (5 items, i.e., *I interrupt others when talking*), inattention (5 items, i. e., *I'm disorganized*), hyperactivity (5 items, i. e., *I seek out fast paced, exciting activities*), and self-concept problems (5 items, i.e., *I wish I had greater confidence in my abilities*), and an ADHD index. Higher punctuations reflect more problems and difficulties. The reliability of the full scale for this study has been quite good ($\alpha = .90$). Total score of the scale and impulsivity and inattention subscales scores were used as dependent variables. Both subscales obtained proper internal consistency ($\alpha = .74$ for impulsivity and $\alpha = .78$ for inattention).

Transdiagnostic variables

Dysexecutive Questionnaire (DEX, Burgess et al., 1996) was used to measure executive functioning. It is a 20 item questionnaire that evaluates dysexecutive deficits. Higher scores indicate a higher deficit, and a score of 24 or higher represents important difficulties. We have used the Spanish scale (Pedrero et al., 2009), with an internal consistency suitable for use ($\alpha = .907$). Total score was used as an independent variable.

Difficulties in working memory and inhibition were measured with the Adult Executive Functioning Inventory (ADEXI, Holst & Thorell, 2016), a 14-item scale that evaluates working memory (total score of 9 items, i. e., *I have difficulty remembering lengthy instructions*) and inhibition (total score of 5 items, i. e., *I sometimes have difficulty refraining from smiling or laughing in situations where it is inappropriate*), aimed at the adult population. Higher scores signify greater deficits. In this research the reliability was very good for working memory ($\alpha = .895$) and right for inhibition ($\alpha = .657$).

To evaluate the use of Emotion Regulation strategies, Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ, Gross & John, 2003) was used. It is a 10-item scale that evaluates two ER strategies. Cognitive re-evaluation (6 items, i. e., *When I want to feel more positive emotion (such as joy or amusement), I change what I'm thinking about*) is a positive strategy, and a high score means no difficulty in ER strategies use. Emotional suppression (4 items, i. e., *I control my emotions by not expressing them*) is a negative ER strategy, so an elevated score indicate problems in the ER strategies choice. For this study both had good internal consistency ($\alpha = .887$ for reevaluation; $\alpha = .826$ for suppression).

Procedure

Data were obtained during January 2020 to March 2020 through a 20-minutes response online questionnaire. This survey collected the main objectives of the work and ensured anonymity, and it was formed by different questionnaires initially designed as “pen-and-paper”. Written informant consent was also obtained. The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Psychopathology Investigation Unit.

Analysis

Statistical analysis package SPSS v.25 was used for data analysis. Pearson correlations were calculated to examine the relationships between the study variables. Multiple regression analyses were performed to see the influence of the transdiagnostic variables (dysexecutive functioning, difficulties in working memory, inhibition, use of ER strategies) on the presence of ADHD symptomatology and its related behaviors. The assumptions of multiple linear regressions (homoscedasticity, multicollinearity and independence from errors) were checked, obtaining adequate values to accept the predictive models as valid.

Results

Correlates of ASD traits and clinical and transdiagnostic variables

Pearson's bivariate correlations (Table 2) showed that a significant relationship between all the variables in the study existed.

The presence of ASD traits correlated positive and significantly with ADHD traits ($r = .519$; $p < .01$). Also, there was a positive and significant correlation between ASD traits and inattention ($r = .312$; $p < .01$) and impulsivity ($r = .442$; $p < .01$).

There was also a positive and significant association between ASD symptomatology and problems in executive functioning ($r = .503$; $p < .01$), working memory deficits ($r = .468$; $p < .01$) and inhibition problems ($r = .239$; $p < .01$). The relationships between ADHD symptoms and these variables were equally positive and significant (executive functioning: $r = .758$; $p < .01$; working memory: $r = .623$; $p < .01$; and inhibition: $r = .532$; $p < .01$).

For the ER strategies variable, as expected, positive and significant relationships were found between ASD traits and emotional suppression ($r = .352$; $p < .01$) and between ADHD features and emotional suppression ($r = .200$; $p < .05$); as well as negative and significant relationships between ASD traits and cognitive re-evaluation ($r = -.208$; $p < .05$), and between ADHD symptoms and this same variable ($r = -.205$; $p < .05$).

Hypothesis 1 was accepted because positive and significant associations were found between ASD and ADHD score, impulsivity and inattention. Also, ASD traits, ADHD features, inattention and impulsivity correlate positive and significantly with the transdiagnostic variables (difficulties in EF and ER).

Predictors of externalizing symptoms

Multiple linear regression analyses (Table 3) showed the predictors for the externalizing symptomatology: ADHD traits, impulsivity and inattention.

The predictive models for ADHD traits and impulsive behaviors were significant ($F = 36.757$, $R^2 = 62.3\%$, $p < .01$ for ADHD symptomatology; $F = 18.249$, $R^2 = 45.1\%$, $p < .01$ for impulsive behaviors). However, this was not the case for inattention ($F = 16.172$, $R^2 = 43\%$, $p = .61$).

As it can be observed in Table 3, transdiagnostic variables were positive and significant predictors of ADHD traits (problems in executive functioning ($\beta = .630$, $t = 6.930$, $p < .01$), working memory deficits ($\beta = .240$, $t = 2.952$, $p < .01$), and difficulties in the use of ER strategies (ERev, $\beta = -.112$, $t = -1.810$, $p < .05$)) and impulsivity behavior in people with high ASD traits (problems in executive functioning ($\beta = .670$, $t = 6.104$, $p < .01$, and difficulties in the use of ER strategies (ERev, $\beta = -.179$, $t = -2.380$, $p < .05$)). They also predicted inattentive behavior problems (executive functioning problems: $\beta = .213$, $t = 1.908$, $p < .05$, and working memory deficits: $\beta = .435$, $t = 4.344$, $p < .01$) but the predictive model was not significant. Therefore, H2 was partially accepted.

Discussion

This research aimed to study BAP in postsecondary students and its relationship with ADHD traits in this population considering a transdiagnostic perspective.

Firstly, it is interesting to highlight the existence of a positive and significant relationship between ASD traits and ADHD traits in the general population. This result, consistent with previous research (Panagiotidi et al., 2017; Polderman et al., 2014), confirms that the co-occurrence of the traits of both disorders is also high in the broad autism phenotype, as it is in people with ASD diagnosis.

There are also significant relationships between both symptoms and the transdiagnostic variables of the study. The positive and significant association between problems in EF, working memory and inhibition for both disorders coincides with other studies (Stewart et al., 2018; Wallace et al., 2016). Problems in EF define both ASD and ADHD symptoms, so this relationship was expected.

Focusing on ER, positive associations with the suppression strategy and negative associations with the cognitive re-evaluation strategy have been found for both disorders. Again, this relationship was expected for ASD traits, coinciding with previous studies (McDonnell & Nuttall, 2018)

For ADHD traits, although present, this relationship is not as significant. However, there are data that report problems in ER in adults with ADHD (Bodalski et al., 2019; Shushakova et al., 2018), so again, this association is understandable.

As far as predictors of externalizing behaviors are concerned, conclusions are in line with expectations. It has been found that most of the transdiagnostic study variables have a predictive role in the presence of these behaviors in people within the broad phenotype. This result is consistent with prior investigations focused on people with ASD, which have found that difficulties in both EF (Pinsonneault et al., 2016) and ER (Bos et al., 2018; Charlton et al., 2019; Weiss, 2014) have a significant role in the presence of externalizing behaviors.

The fact of finding variables that do not have predictive power may be due to the test used. In the case of inhibition, for instance, the use of more extensive tests could influence this result, providing more information.

However, we can affirm that within the BAP the results reported are those expected, and very similar to those given in people with a diagnosis.

Limitations and future directions

Despite the positive results that have been obtained, this study has to be understood within its limitations. With a larger sample, the results could be generalized to a greater extent. In this respect, the sample, college students, is not representative of the total population, so this fact could be an added limitation in the generalization of our results.

Similarly, it would be interesting to evaluate more externalizing behaviors, such as repetitive and stereotyped behaviors, as well as to study other transdiagnostic variables that have a significant role in the appearance of these behaviors in people with ASD, such as intolerance to uncertainty or callous-unemotional traits (Gramszlo et al., 2017; Rodgers et al., 2018), in order to know their role in people without ASD diagnosis.

Also, and as it has been pointed out, the use of other more extensive tests for the evaluation of some of the variables can report more significant conclusions.

Conclusions and implications

The results reported are interesting since they are very similar to those reached in the population with ASD, which reinforces the study of ASD as a dimensional disorder, in line with the latest advances in the classification of psychopathology.

Understanding ASD and ADHD as dimensions allow their main characteristics to be studied and recognized in the general population. Knowing the features of these disorders and the relationship between them in this population group has positive repercussions in several areas of intervention, including education. Considering which variables are behind the problematic behaviors, and their role in their appearance, allows interventions to be focused on these factors, contributing to their reduction. Psycho-educational interventions should consider EF and positive ER strategies training within their planning in order to reduce or prevent the appearance of behavior problems, such as impulsivity. Taking into account the dimensionality of ASD and ADHD, all students would benefit, to a greater or lesser extent, from working on these variables.

The current trend of increased diagnoses of ASD requires preventive and/or palliative actions, with the final objective of improving quality of life. The educational environment is an ideal scenario for working on these aspects, bearing in mind that are certain branches of knowledge that are susceptible to include people with higher features of ASD, such as engineering.

However, it is interesting to continue focusing on the study of ASD and the variables related to this disorder, in order to continue expanding its knowledge, having a positive impact on the whole population.

Acknowledgements

This work has not received any source of funding

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Table 1. Demographic variables.

		N = 117
Gender		
Men		57
Women		60
Chronological age		
M		25.26
SD		4.634
Range		18-30
Studies level		
Higher professional training		26
University		91
Area of knowledge		
Social sciences		28
M		14
W		14
Humanities/arts		18
M		6
W		12
Health sciences		22
M		9
W		13
Sciences		25
M		10
W		15
Engineering		24
M		18
W		6

Notes: M= men, W= women.

Table 2. Means, standard deviation and Pearson correlation matrix for the relationships between ASD symptoms, externalizing behaviors (ADHS impulsivity and inattention) and transdiagnostic variables (N = 117)

	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	M	SD
1: ASD	.519**	.312**	.442**	.503**	.468**	.239**	-.208*	.352**	98.40	18.264
2: ADHD		.782**	.749**	.758**	.623**	.532**	-.205*	.200*	30.91	13.460
3: Inat			.450**	.552**	.610**	.482**	-.139	.171	5.96	3.604
4: Imp				.641**	.418**	.407**	-.249**	.102	4.63	3.095
5: DEF					.639**	.707**	-.090	.281**	20.85	13.376
6: MoW						.560**	-.116	.381**	17.61	6.690
7: Inh							.006	.276**	12.15	3.930
8: ERev								.244**	25.10	8.327
9: ERsup									13.96	5.772

** p < 0.01

* p < 0.05

1= ASD traits measured with BAPQ; 2= ADHD traits measured with CAARS: S; 3= inattention measured with CAARS: S; 4= impulsivity traits measured with CAARS: S; 5= dysexecutive function measured with DEX; 6= working memory measured with ADEXI; 7= inhibition measured with ADEXI; 8= cognitive reappraisal measured with ERQ; 9= emotional suppression measured with ERQ.

Table 3. Summary of Multiple Regression Analyses for Variables Predicting ADHD traits, Impulsivity and Inattention (N = 117)

DV	Predictors variables	R ²	F	β	B	t
ADHD		.623	36.757**			
	DEX			.630	.634	6.930**
	MoW			.240	.483	2.952**
	Inh			-.038	-.131	-.451
	ERev			-.112	-.182	-1.810*
	ERsup			-.031	-.071	-.461
IMP		.451	18.249**			
	DEX			.670	.155	6.104**
	MoW			.017	.008	.178
	Inh			-.067	-.052	-.651
	ERev			-.179	-.066	-2.380*
	ERsup			-.031	-.016	-.383
INAT		.430	16.172			
	DEX			.213	.057	1.908*
	MoW			.435	.234	4.344**
	Inh			.108	.099	1.034
	ERev			-.053	-.023	-.690
	ERsup			-.071	-.045	-.871

** p < 0.01

* p < 0.05

DV = dependent variable; ADHD = ADHD traits; IMP = impulsivity; INAT = inattention; DEX = dysexecutive function measured with DEX; MoW = working memory measured with ADEXI; Inh = inhibition measured with ADEXI; ERev = cognitive reappraisal measured with ERQ; ERsup = emotional suppression measured with ERQ.